

Risk Factors Associated with Diabetic Retinopathy at Muhimbili National Hospital, Tanzania (2023–2025)

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Introduction

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a leading cause of preventable visual impairment, particularly in regions such as sub-Saharan Africa where diabetes mellitus (DM) is rising rapidly amid constrained health systems. Muhimbili National Hospital (MNH), Tanzania's national referral center, increasingly manages advanced DR. This study assessed the burden and determinants of DR among adults attending the MNH ophthalmology clinic.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective cross-sectional review of medical records for adults with diabetes seen between 1 January 2023 and 1 September 2025 was conducted. Records with documented dilated fundus examination were analyzed. Data included socio-demographic characteristics, diabetes type and duration, HbA1c, random glucose, comorbidities (hypertension, dyslipidemia, chronic kidney disease, neuropathy, cardiovascular disease), lifestyle factors (smoking, alcohol use, diet adherence), and DR grading. Analyses used SPSS v24. Chi-square and independent t-tests assessed associations, and variables with $p < 0.20$ were entered into multivariable logistic regression with DR presence as the outcome. Odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were reported.

Results

The analysis comprised 223 patients, of whom 57.0% had diabetes for 20 years or more, and 77.1% demonstrated inadequate glycemic control (HbA1c $> 7\%$). The prevalence of diabetic retinopathy (DR) was 80.7%, with bilateral involvement at 66.8% and vision-threatening DR at 37.2%. In bivariate analyses, DR showed significant associations with advanced age ($p < 0.001$), diabetes type ($p < 0.001$), prolonged duration ($p < 0.001$), inadequate glycemic control ($p = 0.042$), hypertension ($p < 0.001$), dyslipidemia ($p = 0.009$), alcohol consumption ($p = 0.008$), and family history of diabetes ($p = 0.008$). Patients with DR exhibited higher mean HbA1c (8.43% vs 7.78%, $p = 0.014$) and random glucose levels (11.92 vs 10.68 mmol/L, $p = 0.004$). In multivariable regression, hypertension remained the only independent predictor.

Conclusion

DR was extremely common, affecting over four in five patients and with more than one-third presenting with vision-threatening disease—reflecting late presentation and gaps in early detection. Although several factors correlated with DR in unadjusted analyses, hypertension emerged as the dominant independent risk factor.

Keywords

Diabetes, Diabetes Mellitus, Diabetic Retinopathy, Muhimbili, Prevalence, Risk Factors